

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF SALMONELLOSIS DISEASE IN FERGANA CITY AND THE SYSTEM OF ANTI- EPIDEMIC MEASURES

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8013403>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29th May 2023

Accepted: 06th June 2023

Online: 07th June 2023

KEY WORDS

Salmonellosis, epidemiology, hospital, bacterial transmission, source, transitor.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the epidemiology of intestinal infections and measures to combat the epidemic. As the pace of development of economic, social and political processes on a global scale is growing at a rapid pace, it is observed that intestinal infections are also increasing significantly.

Relevance of the topic: prevention of the spread of salmonellosis and improving the quality of medical, veterinary and sanitary services, epidemiological control and implementation of anti-epidemic measures.

Salmonellosis is a disease belonging to the group of intestinal infections, they occur sporadically and in the form of exacerbated diseases. Currently, the widespread promotion of medical culture among people has resulted in the reduction of most intestinal infections. In recent years, it has been recorded that salmonellosis occurs in all countries of the world. As a result of our use of measures against salmonellosis in our republic, the percentage of incidence of the disease among adults and children has decreased. Salmonella are characterized by the fact that they can live in the external environment for a long time, are sensitive to antibiotics, but later the appearance of their antibiotic-insensitive, i.e. resistant strains, animals are manifested mainly in cattle, Avian, food as the main source of salmonellosis in nature.

The fact that people are involved in the spread of salmonellosis infection is primarily determined by the presence of bacterial transport and the separation of salmonellosis from the body at different periods of the disease. Patients with an acute and mild type of salmonellosis, as well as the role of bacteria carriers working in the food enterprise, are extremely important. In the spread of salmonellosis, it was annealed that medical personnel served as a source of infection. After recovery from salmonellosis, a person often remains a carrier of bacteria up to a long time. Salmonellosis sufferers and bacteria carriers are especially epidemiologically dangerous for children under one year of age. With the feces of bacterial carriers, many salmonellyos that are excreted into the external mucit.

The fact that salmonellosis is spread mainly through food makes importance in the reproduction of the disease. Salmonella are found in water in different seasons of the year, in addition to food. In the spread of salmonellosis in hospitals, salmonella infected hands of

mothers and employees, fast food items, towels, underwear, diaper rash, carpet and others play an important role in the domestic-communicable infection of salmonella.

The purpose of the examination: to prevent the role of bacterial carriers in the spread of salmonellosis disease and its occurrence in the form of intra-hospital infection.

Methods of examination: epidemiological and Bacteriological Methods comparative information of salmonellosis disease from infectious intestinal infections on Fergana city for 10 years 2012-2021.

As can be seen from the comparative information:

in 2012, 11.4% in the total absolute indicator 29 intensives, of which children in the absolute indicator 29 in the intensive indicator 42.0;

in 2013 in the total absolute indicator 20 in the intensives indicator 7.5%, of which children in the absolute 26.5% in the indicator 19 intensive indicators, 11.8% in the total absolute indicator;

in 2014, of which 46.3% in the total absolute indicator 34 intensive indicators, 12.1% in the total absolute indicator 35 acute indicators;

in 2015, of which children 41.5% in the total absolute indicator 30 intensive indicators, 9.0% in the total absolute indicator 26;

in 2016, of which children 31.2% in the indicator 24 intensive indicators, total absolute;

in 2017 6.0% in the indicator 18 intensives of which children are 20.0% in the absolute indicator 17 intensives, 5.9% in the total absolute indicator 18 intensives;

in 2018 of which children are 20.4% in the absolute indicator 17 intensives, 3.8% in the total absolute indicator 12 intensives;

in 2019 of which children are 11.0% in the absolute indicator 10 intensives, 7% in the total absolute indicator;

in 2020 of these, 2.2% in the intentionalist index is 6.2% in the children's absolutist index 6 intensive Index, 2.8% in the total absolutist index 9 intentionist index 2021, of which 8.0% in the children's absolutist index 8 intensive index 8;

Results. Comparing the growth and decrease of the disease over the years from the 2012-2013 comparative analysis shows that total salmonellosis disease is -34.2% , of which there is a decrease of -30.1% among children. From a total of +57.3% in 2013-2014, children were observed to increase by +74.7%.

In 2014-2015, the total was -11.4%, of which children decreased by -11.4%.

In 2015-2016, the total was -28.0%, of which children decreased by 24.8%.

In 2016-2017, the total was -34.3%, of which children decreased by 33.1%.

In 2017-2018, the total was -1.7%, of which children decreased by -1.7%.

In 2018-2019, the total was -35.5%, of which children decreased by -44.1%.

In 2019-2020, the total was -42.1%, of which children decreased by 43.6%.

In 2020-2021, a total of +27.0%, of which children were found to have increased by +29.0%.

We can see that salmonellosis decreased by a total of 2.7% in 2020 year compared to 2012 year, compared to 13.5% among children, according to the results of epidemiological analysis and Bacteriological Methods.

Conclusion. As can be seen from the comparative information above, we can see that salmonellosis has significantly decreased in comparison over the years. The correct organization and implementation of measures for the Prevention of salmonellosis in practice is carried out along with employees of Health Protection, Veterinary Services, meat and dairy enterprises, enterprises related to the preparation and distribution of food.

Taking into account the different nebulosity of the epidemiology of salmonellosis, medical and veterinary personnel should always be in strong contact with them in the successful fight against rats. The main force in this work should be aimed at identifying the source of high-burden disease among people, animals, poultry and stopping the spread of the disease in its vaccine. Salmonellosis incidence indicator young children are considering that the high at sanitary Epidemiology Service employees milk for children, dairy products, children liquids used to treat and drink their food are ready to do the work of vegetable, food and pharmacy must control.

The loss of rodents is considered one of the most important measures in the fight against salmonelles, since rats and mice damage animal slaughterhouses, various food objects with Salmonella, causing infection to spread rapidly on livestock and poultry farms. Among agricultural animals, it is necessary to identify and combat salmonellosis bacterial transport, regulate the slaughter of animals in the yard, carry out veterinary examinations before slaughtering animals, normalize the veterinary sanitary regime in places where they use their meat where meat is processed after slaughter, and constantly carry out veterinary sanitary examinations of food. Combating bacterial transport is one of the most important preventive measures. Patients with salmonellosis and carriers of bacteria are hospitalized on the basis of clinical and epidemiological indications.

Children of preschool age carrying bacteria, food enterprises, children and employees of treatment preventive institutions will definitely be hospitalized. In hospitals, epidemiological control over salmonellosis is carried out jointly by employees of the sanitary epidemiological service epidemiologists, sanitary doctors, nutritionists and municipal hygienists, bacteriologists, in which epidemiologists play a key role. As well as establishing epidemiological analysis, training of medical and veterinary specialists to organize seminars on the topic of anti-disease guidance, one of the main measures in preventing the disease is considered.

References:

1. Zueva L.P., Yafaev R.X. Epidemiology. St. Petersburg. Textbook. 2006.
2. Usmanov M.K. Epidemiology. Tashkent Textbook. 1995.
3. Mirtazaev O.M. Manual for practical training from Epidemiology T. 2003.
4. Mamatkulova Mahbuba //To Study Motion of the Grain Mixture on Sieve Surface// INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED RESEARCH IN SCIENCE, ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY. Volume 7, Issue 3, March 2020.
5. Маматкулова Махбуба Тожиалиевна //Изучение многолетней динамики заболеваемости вирусным гепатитом А и оценить эффективности вакцинации// «ИНТЕРНАУКА» *Научный журнал* № 15(144) Апрель 2020 г. Часть 1. 53стр

6. Makhbubakhon Tojialievna Mamatkulova //Determination of Susceptibility of Bacterial Infections to Antibiotics and Prevention of Nosocomial Infections// International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology. Vol. 29, No. 9s, (2020), pp. 4278-4282.
7. Рузибоева Ёркиной Равшановна, Каримов Азизбек Равшанбекович //Факторы, предрасполагающие к развитию рака шейки матки среди женщин Ферганской области за период 2017-2021гг// Международный научно-практический журнал "Интернаука". Вып №12 (235) 2022. 31-32 стр.
8. M.T.Mamatqulova, Y.R.Rosibayeva, S.T.Yulchieva, H.A.Rakhimova //Pregnancy During a Pandemic of Coronavirus Infektion Covid-19 Risks and Effects on the Unborn Child// 2023 International Conferense February 19-23, San Francisco, CA. record number #4222350
9. O.R Parpiyeva, Ostanqulov A.D //Health theory// Международный научно-практический журнал "Форум молодых ученых". Вып №6 (34) 2019. 26-29 page
10. Mamatkulova Makhbuba Tojialievna //THE ROLE OF CYTOGENETIC STUDIES IN CLINICAL MEDICINE// ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. Vol. 11 Issue 1, January 2021.
11. Makhbuba Mamatkulova // Early Prenatal Diagnosis And Prevention Of Birth Damage Development In Children (Spina Bifida - A Defect In The Development Of The Nervous System)// The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research. Vol. 03. Issue 04-16. April 30, 2021. 117-126 pages.
12. Makhamad Tojalievich Toshboltaev, Makhbuba Mamatkulova //NORMATIVE METHOD FOR THE SUBSTANTIATION OF THE COMPOSITION AND QUANTITY OF MACHINES REQUIRED FOR 1000 HECTARES OF COTTON FIELD IN THE CONDITION OF ZBEKISTAN// International Journal of Agriculture, Environment and Bioreserch. Vol. 06, No. 01; 2021. Page 68
13. Маматқулова Махбубахон Тожиалиевна //Фекал орал механизм билан юқувчи ичак инфекцияларининг эпидемиологик тахлили// Журнал «Студенческий вестник» № 17 (67), часть 4, 2019 г.
14. Mamatkulova Makhbuba Tojialievna, Rosibayeva Yorkinoy Ravshanovna //Pregnancy during a pandemic of coronavirus infection COVID-19 risks and effects on the unborn child// Texas Journal of Medical Science. Volume 18. 08-03-2023. 1-5 pages.
15. Тожиалиевна, М.М., & Равшановна, Р.Ё. (2023). ЭНТЕРОВИРУСЛИ КАСАЛЛИКЛАРДАН ВИРУСЛИ ГЕПАТИТ А КАСАЛЛИГИНИНГ КЎП ЙИЛЛИК ДИНАМИКАСИНИ ЎРГАНИШ ВА ИХТИЁРИЙ ЭМЛАШ САМАРАДОРЛИГИГА БАХО БЕРИШ. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(7), 177-180.